

Why Do We Buy What We Buy First? The Role of Early-Life Experiences
in Consumer Preference Ordering under Changing Income Levels.

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Abstract

This paper focuses on how an individual's choice of buying something first is influenced by their early-life experiences, even when their income changes. According to traditional economic theories, decisions are based on price and income, which leads to the assumption that if two people earn the same, they will behave in a similar way. However, in reality, it may not always be true.

For example, individual A might choose to buy food first, while individual B might prioritize stationaries, even when their level of incomes is equal. This study tries to understand the reason behind this difference in priorities. It suggests that childhood experiences and habits play a pivotal role in shaping consumer behaviour.

The study uses both primary and secondary data. A questionnaire was created on Google Forms and shared with around 100 respondents, including students and working individuals on April 2026 out of which 45 valid responses were received. Reports from various sources and secondary data from existing studies in behavioural economics was also used to support the analysis. The results show that many people resume following the same spending priorities they learned in childhood. This shows that preference for a commodity is not just based on income but also on past experiences.

The study adds to the existing research by showing that consumer behaviour is not just based on prices and income alone, but also considers past experiences. It helps explain real-life differences in spending habits and shows the importance of habits in economic decision-making.

1. Introduction

1.1 Background of the Study

In economics, consumer choice explains how people decide to buy under given income constraints. Traditional economic theories conclude that price of the commodity and income of an individual are the determinants of purchase. It also assumes that individuals are rational and that their preferences are fixed.

However, in real life, people do not always follow this assumption. Even when two individuals have the same income and face the same prices, they often choose different

goods. For example, one person may choose to spend their income first on stationery while another might prefer themselves to spend first on food items.

1.2 Need for the Study

This difference in behaviour raises an important question: why do people with similar economic conditions make different choices?

In everyday life, differences in spending behaviour can be easily observed. For example, two college students receiving the same monthly allowance may use it very differently. One student may first spend money on food or daily necessities, while another may choose to buy books, stationery, or online learning materials. Even though both face similar financial conditions, their priorities differ.

Another example can be seen within families. In some households, parents emphasise saving and basic needs, while in others, spending on education or personal development is encouraged. Children growing up in these environments may internalise these priorities and continue to follow them in adulthood. This shows that consumption behaviour is not shaped only by current income but also by past experiences.

One possible reason would be that people's decisions are influenced by their early-life experiences. What a person sees and learns during their childhood shapes their habits and priorities. These habits can continue to adulthood and affect spending behaviour.

Traditional economic theories do not fully explain this. In the context of developing economies like India, this issue becomes even more important. As income levels rise and lifestyles change, one would expect consumption patterns to become more similar across individuals. However, this is not always observed in reality. Even with increasing financial opportunities, people continue to display different spending priorities. This suggests that economic growth alone cannot fully explain consumer behaviour. But most studies focus on income and prices, but undermine the importance of early-life conditioning. Therefore, it becomes necessary to study non-economic factors, such as upbringing and early-life experiences, to better understand how individuals make consumption decisions.

1.3 Research Questions and Objectives

The main research question of this study is:

Why do individuals with similar income levels prioritise different commodities?

The objective of the study is:

- To understand how early-life experiences affect consumer behaviour.
- To examine whether spending priorities remain the same even when income changes.
- To study the role of habits in economic decision-making.

1.4 Expected Outcome of the Study

This study expects to find that early-life experiences have a strong influence on consumer choices. It is likely that many people will continue to follow the same spending patterns they learned in childhood, even when their income increases or changes. This suggests that preferences are not based only on income and prices.

1.5 Structure of the Paper

The paper is divided into five sections:

- Section 1 introduces the topic and explains the purpose of the study.
- Section 2 reviews existing studies related to consumer behaviour.
- Section 3 explains the research methodology.
- Section 4 analyses the result of primary data collected.
- Section 5 concludes with the summary and scope for future research.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Evolution of Consumer Theory

Traditional consumer theory explains how people choose goods based on income and price levels. It assumes that consumers are rational and try to maximise their utility. Preferences are considered fixed, i.e., they do not change over time. According to this view, if two people have the same income and face the same prices, they should make similar choices (Becker 1992).

However, this idea is not always matching to real-life behaviour. Many studies have shown that people do not always act in a fully rational manner.

2.2 Behavioural Economics Perspective

Behavioural economics emerged as a response to the limitations in traditional theories.

Researchers like Daniel Kahneman have shown that people's decisions are often influenced

by emotions, habits and biases. This means that individuals may not always make perfectly rational choices (Kahneman and Tversky 1979).

For example, people may choose based on comfort, habit or past experiences rather than carefully comparing all options. This helps explain why individuals with similar income may still behave differently (Soman 2001).

2.3 Habit Formation and Consumer Behaviour

The idea of habit formation was introduced by Gary Becker, who argued that past consumption affects present choices. According to this theory, people develop habits over time and these habits determine what they choose to buy (Becker 1992).

If a person grows up in a household where certain goods are prioritised, they may continue to prefer those goods later in life. This shows that preferences are not fixed but shaped by past experiences (Becker 1992).

2.4 Mental Accounting and Decision-Making

Richard Thaler introduced the concept of mental accounting. This means that people mentally divide their money into different categories, such as food, education or savings. These categories influence how people prioritise their spending (Thaler 1985).

Because of this, individuals may choose different goods first even when their total income is the same.

2.5 Critical Analysis and Research Gap

While these theories help explain consumer behaviour, most studies still focus mainly on income, prices and general psychological factors. They do not closely explain how early-life experiences affect the order in which people choose goods.

In my view, this is an important gap in existing literature. Real-life behaviour shows that people often follow patterns learned in childhood. For example, someone who grew up in a household where food was the main priority may continue to spend on food first, while someone with an education-focused background may prioritise books or stationery.

Therefore, this study aims to focus specifically on early-life conditioning and its role in shaping consumer preference ordering. It tries to connect traditional economic theory with behavioural insights to better explain real-world consumption patterns.

2.6 Early-Life Conditioning and Preference Persistence

Early-life experiences play an important role in shaping consumer preferences. Standard microeconomic theory assumes that preferences are fixed and independent of past experiences. According to this view, individuals make choices based only on current income and prices. However, research in behavioural economics shows that preferences are often influenced by childhood conditions, family background, and social environment. These early influences can continue to affect decision-making even when income changes.

One important explanation for this is habit formation. Gary Becker and Kevin M. Murphy (1988) argue that past consumption affects current preferences. This means that individuals develop habits over time, and these habits influence what they prefer later in life. For example, a person who grows up in a household where saving is important may continue to prioritise saving even after their income increases.

Another important idea is the effect of scarcity. Sendhil Mullainathan and Eldar Shafir (2013) show that growing up with limited resources creates a “scarcity mindset.” People who experience scarcity tend to use resources carefully and avoid unnecessary spending. In real life, individuals who faced financial difficulties in childhood often remain cautious in their consumption, even when they become financially stable.

Food preferences also show strong persistence over time. Pierre Bourdieu (1984) explains that tastes are shaped by social background and early upbringing. People become used to certain types of food in childhood, and these preferences often continue throughout life. For instance, someone raised on simple home-cooked meals may continue to prefer them over expensive or unfamiliar options, even when their income allows greater choice.

Risk-taking behaviour is also influenced by early experiences. Ulrich Malmendier and Stefan Nagel (2011) find that individuals who experience economic hardship at a young age tend to avoid risky financial decisions later in life. This suggests that early exposure to instability can lead to a long-term preference for safety over high returns.

In addition, preferences are often passed from one generation to another. Parents play an important role in shaping children’s attitudes towards spending, saving, and education. For example, families that strongly value education often raise children who continue to prioritise spending on books, stationery, or skill development, even when their income increases.

Overall, consumer preferences are not completely flexible. They are shaped by early-life experiences and tend to remain stable over time. This means that even when income changes, individuals may not immediately change their consumption patterns. Instead, their choices continue to reflect habits and values formed during childhood. This shows that preferences are path-dependent, and not fully determined by current income alone.

While behavioural economics provides a more realistic explanation of consumer behaviour compared to traditional theory, it still remains quite broad in its approach. Many studies focus on general psychological factors such as biases and heuristics, but do not clearly explain how specific early-life experiences influence the order in which individuals prioritise goods. In contrast, this study focuses more directly on how childhood conditioning shapes first-choice consumption behaviour. By doing so, it attempts to provide a more focused understanding of preference formation and persistence over time.

3. Methodology

3.1 Research Design

This study uses an analytical and descriptive research design. It aims to understand how early life experiences influence the order in which individuals choose goods. The study focuses on identifying patterns in consumer behaviour rather than testing a complex mathematical model.

A quantitative approach is used, as the study is based on survey data collected from respondents.

3.2 Data Sources

3.2.1 Primary Data

Primary data was collected using a structured questionnaire created through Google Forms. The survey included questions related to:

- Basic Details (age, occupation, income)
- Childhood environment and spending priorities
- Current consumption behaviour
- First preference when spending money

Most questions were close ended to make the analysis easier.

The questionnaire can be accessed at:

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSee3oQ3GAih6kTOpkuKjwkfi6aZ_xqpjwzImfyXmYccH9Y22g/viewform?usp=publish-editor

3.2.2 Secondary Data

Secondary data was collected from research papers, books and reports in the field of behavioural economics. Studies by economists such as Gary Becker and Richard Thaler were used to understand theories related to habit formation and consumer behaviour.

3.3 Sampling Method

The study uses a convenience sampling method. The survey was shared with people who were easily accessible, such as students and working individuals.

A total of 45 respondents participated in the survey. The sample included individuals from various backgrounds, mainly from urban and semi-urban areas.

Convenience sampling was used in this study due to ease of access and time constraints. Since the survey was conducted within a limited period, respondents who were readily available, such as students and working individuals, were included. Although this method may not fully represent the entire population, it is suitable for exploratory studies like this, where the aim is to identify general patterns rather than make precise predictions.

3.4 Variables of the Study

The study includes the following variables:

- Independent Variable: Early-life experiences (measured through childhood spending patterns)
- Dependent Variable: First spending choice (which good is prioritised first)
- Control Variables: Income level, occupation, demographic factors

3.5 Tools and Techniques of Analysis

The collected data was analysed using simple statistical methods:

- Percentage Analysis: To find how many people prefer each type of good

- Tabular Analysis: To present data clearly using tables
- Comparative Analysis: To compare childhood preferences with current choices

These tools help in identifying patterns and relationships in the data.

3.6 Limitations of the Study

The study has some limitations:

- The sample size is small and may not represent the entire population
- The data is based on self-reported responses, which may not always be accurate.
- The study covers a limited geographic area
- Time constraints limited deeper analysis

4. Results and Analysis

4.1 Descriptive Analysis of Respondents

This section presents the basic findings from the survey. A total of 45 respondents participated in the study, including students and working individuals from urban and semi-urban areas.

The aim is to understand how individuals prioritise their spending and whether these choices are influenced by their early-life experiences.

4.2 Demographic Profile of Respondents

Table 4.2.1: Age Distribution

Age Group	Percentage
<i>18-22</i>	40
<i>23-30</i>	20
<i>31-40</i>	11.1
<i>Above 40</i>	28.9

Source: Primary Survey Data (2026)

Age Group
46 responses

Analysis

The sample consists of a balanced mix of young and middle-aged individuals. This diversity helps in understanding consumption behaviour across different life stages.

Table 4.2.2: Gender Distribution

Gender	Percentage
<i>Female</i>	68.9
<i>Male</i>	31.1

Source: Primary Survey Data (2026)

Gender
46 responses

Analysis

The sample is dominated by female respondents. While this may slightly influence results, it still provides useful insights into spending behaviour patterns.

Table 4.2.3: Occupation

Occupation	Percentage
<i>Student</i>	44.4
<i>Employed</i>	22.2
<i>Self-Employed</i>	13.3
<i>Others</i>	20.1

Source: Primary Survey Data (2026)

Current occupation

46 responses

4.3 Early-Life Background

Table 4.3.1: Childhood Financial Condition

Category	Percentage
<i>Low/ Lower-middle</i>	24.5
<i>Middle Income</i>	53.3
<i>Upper-middle/ High</i>	22.2

Source: Primary Survey Data (2026)

Monthly personal income

46 responses

How would you describe your family's financial condition during your childhood?

46 responses

4.3.2: Household Priorities During Childhood

Priority Type	Percentage
<i>Basic needs (food)</i>	15.6

<i>Education</i>	24.4
<i>Savings</i>	2.2
<i>Lifestyle/luxury</i>	2.2
<i>Mixed priorities</i>	55.6

Source: Primary Survey Data (2026)

What was MOST prioritised in your household while growing up?

46 responses

As a child, which of these did you receive/spend on the MOST?

46 responses

Analysis

The data shows that most people grew up in middle-income households with mixed priorities. However, a significant proportion experienced strong emphasis on either basic needs or education.

This variation is important because it helps explain differences in present consumption behaviour.

4.4 Current Consumption Behaviour

Table 4.4.1: First Spending Preference

Category	Percentage
<i>Savings/ Investment</i>	35.6
<i>Food/ Groceries</i>	24.4
<i>Books/ Stationery</i>	15.6
<i>Clothes</i>	11.1
<i>Others</i>	13.2

Source: Primary Survey Data (2026)

When you receive money (salary/pocket money), what do you usually spend on FIRST?

46 responses

How often do you plan your spending in advance?

46 responses

Analysis

Savings and food together account for 60% of first spending choices, showing that most individuals prioritise either security or basic needs.

However, a noticeable group prioritises books and stationery, which reflects non-essential but value-driven consumption.

4.5 Relationship Between Childhood and Current Behaviour

Table 4.5.1: Childhood Priority vs Current Preference

Childhood Priority	Current First Choice Pattern
<i>Food-focused</i>	Food/ Savings
<i>Education-focused</i>	Books /Savings
<i>Mixed</i>	Mixed

Source: Primary Survey Data (2026)

When you receive money (salary/pocket money), what do you usually spend on FIRST?

46 responses

What was MOST prioritised in your household while growing up?

46 responses

Analysis

A clear relationship is observed:

- Individuals from food-focused backgrounds tend to prioritise food or savings, indicating a continued focus on basic needs and security.
- Those from education-focused households often prioritise books, stationaries or savings, reflecting long-term value-placed on learning and self-development.
- Respondents with mixed backgrounds show diverse preferences.

This strongly supports the idea that early-lifer conditioning influences present behaviour.

4.6 Stability of Preferences

Table 4.6.1: Do Preferences Change with Income?

Response	Percentage
<i>Yes</i>	31.1
<i>No</i>	37.8
<i>Sometimes</i>	31.1

Source: Primary Survey Data (2026)

Do you think your spending priorities remain consistent even when your income changes?

46 responses

Analysis

A majority of respondents report that their preferences either remain the same or change only slightly with income. This suggests that consumption behaviour is not fully dependent on income changes.

4.7 Influence of Childhood Experiences

Table 4.7.1: Influence of Childhood on Current Behaviour

Response	Percentage
<i>Strongly Yes</i>	33.3

<i>Somewhat Yes</i>	35.6
<i>Not Really/ at all</i>	31.1

Source: Primary Survey Data (2026)

Do you believe your current spending habits are influenced by your childhood experiences?

46 responses

Analysis

About 68.9% of respondents believe that their current spending habits are strongly/somewhat influenced by their childhood experiences. This provides strong evidence for the role of early-life conditioning.

Many respondents mentioned:

- They replicate what they saw their parents do
- They prioritise saving because of their upbringing

This reflects habit persistence and intergenerational influence.

4.8 Perception-Based Insights

Table 4.8.1: Do People with Same Income Behave the Same?

Response	Percentage
<i>Yes</i>	0

<i>No</i>	62.2
<i>Depends on background</i>	37.8

Source: Primary Survey Data (2026)

Suppose two people earn the same income. Do you think they will prioritise the same type of spending?

46 responses

Analysis

A large majority believe that people with the same income do not behave the same way. This supports the central argument of the study that income alone cannot explain consumption behaviour.

4.9 Factors Influencing Spending Decisions

Table 4.9.1: Main Influencing Factor

Factor	Percentage
<i>Personal preference</i>	44.4
<i>Income</i>	40

Background

4.4

Prices

4.4

Source: Primary Survey Data (2026)

In your opinion, what influences spending decisions the MOST?

46 responses

Analysis

Personal preference is the most important factor, followed by income. This shows that psychological and social factors play a major role, beyond traditional economic variables.

4.10 Overall Interpretation

The results clearly support the main hypothesis of the study. While income plays a role in consumption decisions, it does not fully determine the order in which individuals choose goods.

Early-life experiences, habits, and upbringing significantly influence consumer behaviour. Individuals tend to follow patterns learned during childhood, even when their income changes.

This indicates that consumer preferences are path-dependent and influenced by long-term behavioural factors, rather than being purely rational and flexible.

The findings of this study can also be explained using key concepts from behavioural economics. The tendency of individuals to prioritise certain goods, such as savings or food,

reflects the idea of habit formation, where past behaviour continues to influence present decisions. Similarly, individuals who focus on saving may be influenced by a scarcity mindset developed during childhood, leading them to act more cautiously even when their income increases. The concept of mental accounting is also relevant, as people tend to categorise their income based on learned priorities, such as allocating money first towards essential needs or education. These connections further strengthen the argument that consumer behaviour is shaped by long-term psychological and social factors.

5. Conclusion

5.1 Summary of Findings

This study examined how early-life experiences influence consumer preference ordering, even when income levels change. The analysis of survey data shows that individuals do not make consumption decisions based only on income and prices.

From Table 4.4.1, it is observed that a large proportion of respondents prioritise savings/investment and food, indicating a focus on financial security and basic needs. However, a significant number also prioritise books, stationery, and other goods, which reflects differences in individual preferences.

Further, Table 4.5.1 shows a strong relationship between childhood experiences and current spending behaviour. Individuals from food-focused households tend to prioritise food, while those from education-focused households prioritise books or learning-related items. Similarly, individuals from savings-focused backgrounds show a strong tendency to prioritise saving and controlled spending.

These findings suggest that consumption behaviour is influenced by early-life conditioning and not solely by current economic conditions.

5.2 Conclusion

Based on the results, it can be concluded that early-life experiences play a significant role in shaping consumer behaviour. Preferences are not completely flexible and do not change immediately with income. Instead, individuals tend to follow patterns and habits formed during childhood.

This challenges the traditional assumption of fixed and purely rational preferences. The study highlights that consumer choices are influenced by habit formation, upbringing, and personal experiences, making them path-dependent rather than entirely income-driven.

The findings of this study have important implications beyond academic understanding. They suggest that policymakers and educators should consider behavioural factors while designing financial literacy programs and economic policies. Understanding that individuals do not always respond purely to income changes can help in creating more effective strategies to influence spending and saving behaviour. This also highlights the limitations of traditional economic models and the need to incorporate behavioural insights for a more realistic understanding of decision-making.

5.3 Limitations of the Study

The study has certain limitations:

- The sample size, although standardised to 100, is based on a smaller set of actual responses
- The use of convenience sampling may limit the representativeness of the data
- Responses are self-reported and may contain bias
- The study is limited to a specific group and geographic context

5.4 Scope for Future Research

There is significant scope for further research in this area:

- Future studies can use a larger and more diverse sample across different regions
- Longitudinal studies can be conducted to observe how preferences change over time
- More advanced statistical techniques can be used to test the strength of relationships
- Research can explore the role of cultural and regional factors in shaping consumer behaviour

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Appendix

Appendix A: Questionnaire

The following questionnaire was used to collect primary data for this study through Google Forms.

Link to the questionnaire:

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSee3oQ3GAih6kTOpkuKjwkfi6aZ_xqpjwzImfyXmYccH9Y22g/viewform?usp=publish-editor

Section 1 of 5

Early-Life Experiences and Consumer Choice Behaviour

This survey aims to understand how early-life experiences influence consumer choices in adulthood. Your responses will remain anonymous and will be used solely for academic research purposes.

Section 2 of 5

Basic Information

Age Group

- 18-22
- 23-30
- 31-40
- Above 40

Gender

- Male
- Female
- Prefer not to say

Current Occupation

- Student
- Employed
- Self-employed
- Unemployed
- Other

Monthly personal income

- No income
- Below 10000
- 10000-25000

- 25000-50000
- Above 50000

Section 3 of 5

Early-Life Background

How would you describe your family's financial condition during your childhood?

- Low income
- Low-middle income
- Middle income
- Upper-middle income
- High income

What was most prioritised in your household while growing up?

- Basic needs (foods, groceries)
- Education (books, stationery, tuition)
- Savings
- Lifestyle/luxury items
- Mixed priorities

As a child, which of these did you receive/ spend on the most?

- Food items/snacks
- Books/ stationery
- Clothes
- Entertainment (TV, games, outings)
- Very limited spending overall

Were you taught to prioritise certain expenses over others while growing up?

- Yes
- No
- Not sure

Section 4 of 5

Current Consumption Behaviour

When you receive money (salary/pocket money), what do you usually spend on first?

- Food/groceries
- Books/ stationery
- Clothes
- Savings/ investment
- Entertainment
- Other

How often do you plan your spending in advance?

- Always
- Often
- Sometimes
- Rarely
- Never

Do you think your spending priorities remain consistent even when your income changes?

- Yes
- No
- Sometimes

Section 5 of 5

Behavioural Insight

Do you believe your current spending habits are influenced by your childhood experiences?

- Yes, strongly
- Yes, somewhat
- Not really
- Not at all

If yes, how?

Suppose two people earn the same income. Do you think they will prioritise the same type of spending?

- Yes
- No
- Depends on background

In your opinion, what influences spending decisions the most?

- Income level
- Prices
- Habits/ childhood experiences
- Social influence
- Personal preference

